

Chemical cleaning of reverse osmosis membranes fouled by dye bath effluent of a carpet manufacturing plant

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One of the limiting factors in membrane technology is fouling. Fouling results in reducing the flux due to precipitation of feed materials. This problem may be minimized with manipulation of some operating factors such as high cross flow velocity. However fouling occurs even at high cross flow velocity.

In this work the chemical cleaning of membranes fouled with textile dyes has been investigated. The optimum operating conditions were obtained for this process. Increasing the applied pressure results in more fouling and flux declines faster compared to lower pressure.

Reverse osmosis membranes fouled with dye bath effluent. The fouled membranes were chemically cleaned. Acids, alkaline, surface active agent and chelants at different concentrations were used as cleaning agents. For determination of cleaning efficiency, "flux recovery" and "resistance removal" were calculated for all cleaning agents. Cleaning efficiency depends on the type of the cleaning agents and their concentration. The concentration that provides the highest cleaning efficiency can be considered as the optimum concentration.

Membrane filtration has been used for treatment of various feeds. Depending on the membrane type, materials in the feed and process conditions the membrane loses its performance during time. Flux, a measure for membrane performance is controlled by two phenomena, concentration polarization and fouling¹. Based on the terminology introduced by IUPAC, fouling is "a process resulting in loss of performance of a membrane due to the deposition of suspended or dissolved substances on external surface, at its pore openings or within its pores"². Numerous researches are carried out around the world for fouling reduction and cleaning of the fouled membranes. Control of fouling is of utmost importance. Technique involved are pre-treatment of feed, which reduces the particulate density, optimisation of operating condition, e.g. moderate pressure, cross flow and backwashing and membrane regeneration.

An important technique for membrane regeneration is chemical cleaning of fouled membrane. Cleaning is defined as "a process where material is relieved of a substance, which is not being an integral part of the material"³.

Cleaning methods used for RO membrane restoration could be broadly categorized into three types : (A) Physical cleaning, (B) Chemical cleaning and (C) Physio-chemical cleaning.

An important technique for membrane regeneration is chemical cleaning of fouled membranes. Chemical cleaning means removing impurities by means of chemical agents.

A literature review for research work and experiences in membrane cleaning and restoration revealed that chemicals are widely used for membrane cleaning and regeneration. Most of the manufactures recommend chemical methods for cleaning and regeneration of the membranes.

The first step in chemical cleaning of a membrane is finding a suitable chemical as a cleaning agent. The choice of a cleaning agent depends on material in feed, type of the deposit and membrane resistance. The selection is mainly based on trial and error.

Cleaning consumes time and money. About 5–20% of the operating cost is the cost of cleaning⁴. This shows the importance of the continuous research in this field.

Despite the success of cleaning methods in membrane restoring, up to now there are some problems associated with membrane cleaning. Cleaning procedures need long operation time⁵, consume chemicals⁶, degrade some membranes⁷ and may cause corrosion in the system⁸.

The development of new-generation membranes that can tolerate wide pH ranges, higher temperatures, and harsh

Madaeni *et al.* : Chemical cleaning of reverse osmosis membranes fouled by dye bath effluent of a carpet *etc.*

chemical environments and that have improved water flux and solute rejection characteristics have resulted in many applications for the reverse osmosis (RO) process. One of the applications of reverse osmosis is in textile wastewater treatment, to remove colour. In this application fouling restricts membrane performance.

Other membrane processes such as ultrafiltration has been successfully employed for recycling high molecular weight and insoluble dyes (e.g. indigo, disperse), auxiliary chemicals (polyvinyl alcohol) and water^{9,10}. However, ultrafiltration does not remove low molecular weight and soluble dyes¹¹. Efficient color removal has been achieved by nanofiltration and reverse osmosis¹².

Akbari *et al.*¹³ investigated the treatment of textile dye effluent using a polyamide-based nanofiltration membrane. Their experiments were run with seven dyes and a nanofiltration membrane (Desal 5DK). The effects of concentration, pH and salt on flux and retention were studied. The cut-off of the membrane explains that the retention of the relative high molecular weight dyes (as direct red 80 or direct yellow 8) is always almost 100%. For anionic dyes as acid orange 10 or acid red 4, the amphoteric nature of polyamide explains the lower retention at pH 3 than 6. This effect is more pronounced and reversed for basic blue 3, a cationic dye. The membrane is sensitive to fouling since most of the dyes are used for polyamide textile dyeing. Moreover, the presence of salt leads to a further decrease in flux.

Noël *et al.*¹⁴ have evaluated the performance of two types of membrane (NF45 and BQ01) for a direct dye solution. They applied an electric field to eliminate fouling problems. Electro-nanofiltration performance was quantified for different potentials and concentrations. An electric field was found to be efficient in reducing fouling for both membranes studied. They also noticed that direct dye solution fouling changes the NF45 membrane into a reverse osmosis membrane, while the permeability of the second membrane was enhanced.

Ratana *et al.*¹⁵ have studied three nanofiltration membranes for the treatment of effluents containing salt and reactive dye. The membranes were ES20, NTR-729HF and LES90. ES20 and LES90 are negatively charged membranes and NTR-729HF, a substituted polyvinyl alcohol membrane, is neutral. It was observed that the ES20 and LES90 membranes can effectively retain color, producing a permeate suitable for reuse. They also noted that for feed containing salt and dye, the transmembrane osmotic pressure difference is enhanced, resulting in a substantial flux

decline. The presence of dye in the effluent significantly affects the salt removal effectiveness of ES20 and LES90.

Van der Bruggen *et al.*¹⁶ investigated mechanisms of retention and flux decline for the nanofiltration of dye baths from the textile industry. The mechanisms involved in this process are not clearly understood and the practical application of the process is facing many problems such as fouling and flux decline. The mechanisms of retention and flux decline were examined using two different approaches. Firstly, synthetic dye baths were prepared according to the manufacturer's recipes. Retention of two reactive dyes (reactive blue 2 and reactive orange 16) was studied in separate baths and with different concentrations of Na₂SO₄, Na₂CO₃, NaOH and a surfactant. Different nanofiltration membranes (UTC-60, NF70 and NTR 7450) were used. The water flux in each of the experiments was monitored. It was found that the retention of ions decreased with the ion concentration due to a decrease of the Donnan potential. The retention of the dyes was high and was not influenced by the dye concentration or the ionic strength. The water flux was dependent on the ion concentration in the feed solution : high ion concentrations caused a dramatic decrease of the water flux. The dye concentration in the bath was found to have only a minor influence, whereas surfactants did not change water flux or dye retention. In a second step, an industrial wastewater from a textile factory was treated biologically in an active sludge system. The effluent was used as feed for nanofiltration with the same membranes as in the first step. The overall results for these experiments were satisfactory. The ion concentration was much lower than in the earlier experiments due to mixing of different feed streams. Therefore, the water fluxes were not considerably lower compared with the clean water fluxes. The retentions were sufficiently high to make recirculation of the treated water possible, thereby providing a considerable saving of water.

Yu *et al.*¹⁷ used nanofiltration for desalination and concentration in dye production. A dye-producing plant using nanofiltration membrane technology for the desalting and concentrating of aqueous dye was designed and built in China in 1993. The membrane system can produce aqueous dye with more than 25% dye and about less than 1% salt content. The improved process using nanofiltration membrane technology is continuous and automatic in operation. It produces dye products with high purity and consistent quality.

Xu *et al.*¹⁸ investigated nanofiltration of a high-formula-weight dye, Cibacron F3G-A, FW = 840, low- to intermediate cross flow velocity and pressure using a zirconium hy-

drous oxide-poly (acrylic acid) membrane. A sharp minimum in the rejection vs pressure curves obtained at constant cross flow velocities provided a distinct determination of the pressure required initiating dynamic membrane formation. These minima occurred at a pressure near 2 MPa and only at a cross flow velocity less than 0.4 m/s, indicating that a critical pressure is required for membrane formation while also implying that the concentration at the membrane surface is involved in the modification.

In this work the chemical cleaning of reverse osmosis membranes fouled by a dye bath effluent is explained. Operating conditions for reducing the membrane fouling have been determined. The effects of four chemical agents and their concentrations have been studied. In addition to the type and concentration of chemical agent, the effect of cleaning time was also investigated.

Results and discussion

Determination of optimum operating conditions :

The hydrodynamics factors i.e. cross flow velocity and transmembrane pressure play an important role in flux pattern and fouling characteristics. The effects of cross flow velocity and transmembrane pressure on flux and fouling were investigated.

Effect of pressure on cake resistance :

One of the factors that affect the fouled layer compression is operating pressure. By increasing the pressure, the cake resistance is increased. For showing the effect of pressure on cake resistance R_f/R_m (overall fouling), where R_f and R_m denote to deposit resistance and membrane resistance respectively, as a function of transmembrane pressure after 150 min, has been plotted (Fig. 1). Usually by increasing the transmembrane pressure cake resistance is increased. This behavior has been shown clearly in Fig. 1.

Effect of pressure on flux :

The transmembrane pressures up to 20 bars caused an increase in flux. For transmembrane pressures upper than 20 bars flux does not show an expected increase with ΔP . High pressure results in an increase in both reversible and irreversible fouling so flux decreases.

Effect of cross flow velocity on flux :

Cross flow velocity is able to prevent fouling. Usually high cross flow velocity causes a turbulency and results in an increment in mass transfer. With decreasing the cross-flow velocity, turbulency is decreased and better condition for fouling is provided so a decline in flux is existed at lower crossflow velocity.

Fig. 1. R_f/R_m as a function of transmembrane pressure.

Fouling and cleaning procedure :

Some conditions are required for fouling that must be provided prior to the cleaning. In order to provide these operating conditions for fouling, cross flow velocity of around 0 m/s and operating pressure of 24 ± 2 bar were chosen. In these operating conditions at 150 min fouling was occurred.

The fouled membranes were cleaned according to the following protocol suggested by Fane and his colleagues¹⁹. Before and after fouling the water flux of the membrane was measured by passing distilled water through the membrane (initial water flux = J_{wi} , water flux after fouling = J_{wf}). The fouled membrane was washed with distilled water for 10 min to remove unbounded substances from the membrane surface. The water flux was measured after washing (J_{ww}). This was followed by washing the membrane with a cleaning agent for a specific time (10 min) without applying pressure. Membrane was washed again with distilled water to remove any chemical agent for a specific time (5 min). The water flux after chemical cleaning was determined (J_{wc}). Fig. 2 is a schematic representation of cleaning procedure.

Fouling and cleaning quantification :

Fouling can be quantified by the resistance appearing during the filtration and cleaning can be specified by the removal of this resistance. The resistance is due to the formation of a cake or gel layer on the membrane surface. The flux (J), through the cake and the membrane, may be described by Darcy's law :

$$J = \frac{\Delta P}{\mu \Sigma R} \quad (1)$$

In which ΔP is transmembrane pressure (driving force), μ is viscosity of the fluid and ΣR is sum of the resistances. Membrane resistance (R_m) can be estimated from the initial water flux :

Madaeni *et al.* : Chemical cleaning of reverse osmosis membranes fouled by dye bath effluent of a carpet *etc.*

$$R_m = \frac{\Delta P}{\mu J_{wi}} \quad (2)$$

The resistance, which is appeared after fouling (R_f), can be calculated from the water flux after washing with water :

$$R_f = \left(\frac{\Delta P}{\mu J_{ww}} \right) - R_m \quad (3)$$

The resistance, which is remained after cleaning (R_c), can be calculated from the water flux after chemical cleaning :

$$R_c = \left(\frac{\Delta P}{\mu J_{wc}} \right) - R_m \quad (4)$$

Resistance removal (RR), which is a tool for cleaning quantification, can be estimated from :

$$RR (\%) = \left(\frac{R_f - R_c}{R_f} \right) \times 100 \quad (5)$$

Flux recovery (FR) is another method for quantification of cleaning efficiency :

$$FR (\%) = \left(\frac{J_{wc} - J_{ww}}{J_{wi} - J_{ww}} \right) \times 100 \quad (6)$$

Both of the parameters i.e. resistance removal and flux recovery have been used for demonstrating the cleaning efficiency^{19,20}.

Fig. 2. Schematic of cleaning protocol

Flux behavior versus time during fouling operation :

Generally, flux declines with time due to deposition of feed's material on the membrane surface. Fig. 3 shows this behavior during time for FT30 reverse osmosis membrane. During this experiment the cross flow velocity was approximately zero. Initial flux (zero time) is the flux of distilled water. As is expected permeate flux is much lower than pure water flux because of high osmotic pressure in the feed. The initial flux is high but it drops quickly and decreases gradually.

Chemical cleaning :

Four types of chemical agents i.e. acids, bases, surfactants, and chelants were used in these experiments.

Fig. 3. Behavior of flux versus time ($\Delta P = 24$ bar, $V \sim 0$ m/s).

Fig. 4. Effect of HCl concentration on resistance removal.

Comparison of acids in cleaning efficiency :

Fig. 4 demonstrates the ability of HCl to clean the membrane. With increasing the concentration the cleaning efficiency is increased.

Efficiency of H_2SO_4 is presented in Fig. 5. The optimum concentration (the concentration which provides maximum efficiency) is 0.1%. The first part of the curve (in-

creasing efficiency with concentration) is anticipated. More chemical results in more removal of foulants. However decreasing the efficiency with increasing the concentration, probably is due to the permeability of the cake layer. In general, cleaning may remove the deposit layer or alter its permeability. Increasing the concentration of cleaning agent up to the optimum concentration provides maximum voidage and highest cleaning efficiency and/or may decrease with further increase in chemical concentration, which results in lower cleaning efficiency.

Fig. 5. Effect of H_2SO_4 concentration on resistance removal.

HNO_3 was also used for cleaning. The efficiency is not high. In the low concentration HNO_3 has a negative effect on the cleaning. This may be due to more fouling caused by the materials used.

Comparison of alkaline in cleaning efficiency :

Both NaOH and KOH demonstrate a dominant effect in cleaning of the fouled membranes NaOH showed complete removal efficiency. KOH demonstrated high but not a complete effect. NH_4OH showed a low effect probably due to the weakness of NH_4OH .

Comparison of chelants in cleaning efficiency :

In addition to strong acids and alkaline, chelants were also used to remove deposit from the surface of fouled membranes. In this step two chelants were employed. EDTA demonstrated moderate effect as a cleaning agent. Citric acid played a bad role in chemical cleaning (Fig. 6). This can be attributed to decreasing the cake voidage formed on the membrane surface.

Comparison of surface-active agents in cleaning efficiency :

In this step two types of surface-active agents (surfactants) were used. SDS showed a low but constant effect. This is due to limited ability of SDS as a cleaning agent. Triton X-100 demonstrated a negative effect on fouled membrane. This can be attributed to decreasing of cake voidage formed on the membrane surface.

Fig. 6. Effect of citric acid concentration on resistance removal.

Comparison of four types of cleaning agents :

A comparison between four types of chemical agent is illustrated in Fig. 8. Acid and alkaline showed significant effect compare to the other types of chemical agents. The effect of alkaline in cleaning of organic foulant is better than acids²¹.

Effect of time on cleaning efficiency :

Cleaning time affects the cleaning efficiency. Generally if cleaning time is increased, the efficiency will be increased. However the effect is reduced gradually. Fig. 8 indicates the time effect on cleaning. With increasing the cleaning time, resistance removal is increased. The effect is limited due to limited ability of cleaning agent for cake removal.

Fig. 7. Comparison of acid, alkaline, chelants, and surfactants for resistance removal in 0.1%.

Conclusions :

The illustrated experiments showed that :

Some operating factors such as transmembrane pressure and cross flow velocity are effective in fouling reduction; With increasing the transmembrane pressure cake resistance is increased; Chemical cleaning of fouled membrane is a good process for regeneration of fouled membrane; Alkaline are more effective in chemical cleaning of dye bath effluents compare to the other chemical types tested in this study (i.e. acids, chelants and surfactants); Generally with

Fig. 8. Effect of cleaning time on resistance removal.

Fig. 9. Schematic of the experimental set up : (1) feed tank, (2) pump, (3) valve, (4) pressure gauge, (5) crossflow cell, (6) membrane, (7) permeate, (8) balance, (9) concentrate, (10) by-pass.

increasing the concentration of cleaning agent the effectiveness of cleaning is increased; Ability of some chemicals is restricted so increasing the concentration has no effect; Time is an important factor in chemical cleaning.

Experimental

All experiments were carried out in a reverse osmosis rig (Fig. 9) in 28° using FT30 polyamide composite membrane from FILMTEC (United States). The membrane area was 0.002 m². Flux was calculated by measuring the perme-

ate weight.

The feed was a colored solution of dye bath effluent of "Farsh-e-Gharb" carpet manufacturing plant (Kermanshah, Iran). To facilitated fouling condition 3.5 grams of dye was added to 5 liter of effluent solution.

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